

BUG'DOY NAVLARI YER USTKI QISMINING O'SISH KO'RSATKICHLARIGA AZOTOBACTER 2018 SHTAMINING TA'SIRI

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15543230>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda *Azotobacter 2018* shtamining 11 xil bug'doy navi yer ustki qismining dastlabki o'sishiga ta'siri laboratoriya sharoitida baholandi. Bir haftalik kuzatuv davomida poya uzunligi o'lchandi va nazorat hamda inokulyatsiya qilingan guruhlar o'rtasidagi farqlar statistik tahlil qilindi. Natijalar scatter plot va issiqlik xaritasi orqali vizualizatsiya qilindi. "Asr", "O'zbekiston-25" va "Yog'du" navlarida sezilarli ijobiy ta'sir, "Andijon-2" navida esa salbiy natija kuzatildi. Tadqiqot biologik stimulyatorlarning navlar kesimida turlicha samaradorligini ko'rsatadi hamda seleksiya va agrotexnik tadbirlarda ularning qo'llanilishi uchun ilmiy asos bo'la oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Azotobacter*, biologik inokulyatsiya, poya uzunligi, *Triticum aestivum* L

Аннотация. В данном исследовании изучено влияние штамма *Azotobacter 2018* на начальный рост надземной части 11 сортов пшеницы в лабораторных условиях. В течение недели измерялась высота растений, а различия между контрольной и обработанной группами были проанализированы статистически. Результаты визуализированы с помощью диаграмм рассеяния и тепловой карты. Существенный положительный эффект отмечен у сортов «Аср», «Узбекистан-25» и «Йогду», в то время как сорт «Андижан-2» показал отрицательный результат. Исследование подтверждает различную эффективность *Azotobacter* в зависимости от сорта и обосновывает его перспективность для селекции и агротехнических мероприятий.

Ключевые слова: *Azotobacter*, биологическая инокуляция, длина стебля, *Triticum aestivum* L.

Abstract. This study evaluated the effect of *Azotobacter* strain 2018 on the early shoot growth of 11 wheat varieties under laboratory conditions. Plant height was measured over one week, and differences between control and inoculated groups were statistically analyzed. Results were visualized using scatter plots and heatmaps. Significant positive effects were observed in varieties "Asr", "Uzbekistan-25", and "Yogdu", while a negative effect was noted in "Andijon-2". The study highlights the variable effectiveness of *Azotobacter* across different varieties and supports its potential use in breeding and agronomic practices.

Keywords: *Azotobacter*, biological inoculation, stem length, *Triticum aestivum* L.

Bug'doy (*Triticum aestivum* L.) dunyodagi eng muhim oziq-ovqat ekinlaridan biri hisoblanadi [1] va O'zbekistonda ham aholini don mahsulotlari bilan ta'minlashda asosiy o'rinni egallaydi [2]. Bugungi kunda, global iqlim o'zgarishlari, qishloq xo'jalik yerlarining

degradatsiyasi va tuproq unumdorligining pasayishi sharoitida bug'doy hosildorligini oshirish dolzarb muammolardan biri bo'lib qolmoqda. Shu bilan birga, zamonaviy qishloq xo'jaligida kimyoviy o'g'itlar va pestitsidlarning haddan tashqari qo'llanilishi atrof-muhit va inson salomatligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda [3]. *Azotobacter chroococcum* — bu *Pseudomonasaceae* oilasiga mansub *Azotobacter* jinsining azotni biriktiruvchi rizobakteriyasi hisoblanadi [4]. Ular nafaqat o'simliklarni azot bilan ta'minlaydi, balki o'sishni stimullovchi gormonlar, vitaminlar va boshqa biologik faol moddalarni ishlab chiqarish orqali o'simliklarning o'sishi va rivojlanishiga ham ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi [4, 5, 6]. *Azotobacter* tomonidan ishlab chiqarilgan EPS turli maqsadlarda, jumladan, og'ir metallarning biosorbsiyasi va nano-biomateriallar bioishlab chiqarilishida qo'llanilgan [7].

Azotobacter shtamlari turli ekologik sharoitlarda turlicha samaradorlik ko'rsatadi va ularning ta'siri o'simlik navlariga qarab sezilarli darajada farqlanishi mumkin [8]. Shuning uchun ham, ma'lum bir sharoitda va muayyan navlarda qo'llash uchun eng samarali shtamlarni aniqlash muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bu o'z navbatida, ushbu shtamlarning ta'sir mexanizmlarini va samaradorligini baholashga qaratilgan tadqiqotlar o'tkazish zaruriyatini keltirib chiqaradi. Ushbu tadqiqotda, *Azotobacter* 2018 shtamining turli bug'doy navlarining erta o'sish fazasidagi rivojlanishiga ta'sirini o'rganish maqsad qilib olindi. Adabiyotlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, *Azotobacter* bakteriyalari tuproqda erkin yashovchi, azotni fiksatsiya qiluvchi bakteriyalar hisoblanadi. Ular nafaqat atmosfera azotini o'zlashtirib, tuproqni azot bilan boyitadi, balki o'simlik o'sishini rag'batlovchi gormonlar (auksinlar, gibberellinlar, sitokininlar) ham hosil qiladi [9]. *Azotobacter chroococcum* shtammlarining bug'doy o'simligiga ta'siri Kizilkaya (2008) tomonidan o'rganilgan bo'lib, bakterial inokulyatsiya don hosildorligini 97% va somon hosildorligi esa 33% ga oshirgani qayd etilgan. Mahato va boshqalar olimlarning tadqiqotlarida *Azotobacter* bakteriyalari bug'doy ildiz tizimini yaxshilash bilan birga, o'simlikning yer ustki qismini o'sishini ham rag'batlantirishi aniqlangan [10, 11, 12, 13]. Razmjooei (2022) tadqiqotlarida *Azotobacter* turli xil ozuqaviy qiymati va sifat darajalarida o'simliklarga qanday ta'sir qilishi o'rganilgan, unga ko'ra 200 mg/l azot darajasida peroksidaza (POD) faolligi 95.4% ga ortgan.

Tadqiqotimizda bug'doyning (*Triticum aestivum* L.) 11 xil navi ishlatildi. Tajriba laboratoriya sharoitida o'tkazilib, urug'lar 2025-yil 20-mart kuni tuvaklarga ekildi. Tajriba ikkita guruhdan iborat bo'lib, nazorat guruhi faqat suv bilan sug'orildi (3 ta tuvak), tajriba guruhi esa *Azotobacter* 2018 shtami suv bilan 1:1 nisbatda aralastirilib inokulyatsiya qilindi (6 ta tuvak). O'simliklarning poya uzunligi 2025-yil 25-mart va 28-mart kunlari o'lchandi. O'lchovlar tuproq sathidan boshlab o'simlikning ko'rinib turgan eng yuqori nuqtasigacha standart o'lchov asbobi yordamida amalga oshirildi. To'plangan ma'lumotlar *Azotobacter* inokulyatsiyasining bug'doy poyasining o'sishiga ta'sirini aniqlash uchun statistik jihatdan tahlil qilindi.

Olingan natijalar statistik tahlil usullari yordamida nazorat va tajriba guruhlari orasidagi farqlarni aniqlash uchun qayta ishlandi. Farqlarning ahamiyati standart statistik vositalar yordamida aniqlangan. Shuningdek, tajriba va nazorat ko'rsatkichlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni aniqlash uchun tarqalish diagrammasi (scatter plot) analizi o'tkazildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, *Azotobacter* 2018 shtami bug'doyning ayrim navlarida yer ustki qismining o'sishini rag'batlantiradi. Xususan, "Asr", "O'zbekiston-25" va "Yog'du" navlari *Azotobacter* inokulyatsiyasiga ijobiy javob berib, nazorat guruhiga nisbatan yuqori o'sish ko'rsatkichlarini namoyish etdi. Shu bilan birga, "Andijon-2" navi ushbu shtamm

ta'sirida aksincha, past o'sish ko'rsatkichlarini qayd etdi. Bu esa Azotobacter shtammlarining samaradorligi o'simlik naviga bog'liq ekanligini yana bir bor tasdiqlaydi.

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